

Batch-querying Strategies in Bayesian Active Learning Isolation Forests

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Abstract: In Active Learning, it is beneficial to acquire labels in batches to optimize labeling time. However, naive query strategies designed for single queries tend to fail in settings with data redundancy. This paper proposes a batch-querying strategy for Bayesian Active Learning in Isolation Forests (BALIF), which currently relies on sequential single-point queries, and compares it to two existing strategies (BALD and BatchBALD). Experiments on multiple Anomaly Detection benchmark datasets with data duplication demonstrate superior performance of our method. By selecting samples in batches, the method engages domain experts through a single interaction per cycle, ensuring a more efficient use of their expertise.

Keywords: Active Learning, Anomaly Detection, Batch querying, Isolation Forest

1. INTRODUCTION

Anomaly Detection (AD) is a well-established area of Machine Learning that aims to identify data points that significantly deviate from expected behavior (Chandola et al., 2009). These anomalies often signal rare high-impact events, making their detection critically important. For instance, in cybersecurity, anomalies may signal network breaches or intrusions (Yang et al., 2022); in industrial systems, they can reveal irregularities in sensor readings indicative of potential equipment failures (Cook et al., 2020); and in healthcare, anomalies may correspond to unusual physiological signals, such as abnormal heart rates (Sabic et al., 2021).

These examples highlight the broad applicability and importance of AD in various fields. However, defining an anomaly is often nontrivial. In fact, anomalies are highly context-dependent; what is considered abnormal in one scenario may be entirely expected in another. Their interpretation often relies on domain expertise and evolving user needs, making it difficult to establish a consistent definition (Zipfel et al., 2023). Moreover, creating labeled datasets for AD tasks can be challenging due to the scarcity, ambiguity, and high annotation cost of anomalous instances (Zschech et al., 2019). As a result, unsupervised models such as Isolation Forest (IF) (Liu et al., 2009) are commonly used, but often fail to incorporate user-specific definitions of anomalies.

One way to address this limitation is to integrate Active Learning (AL) into AD. AL is a Machine Learning approach in which the model actively queries the user or domain expert for labels of informative data points (Pelleg and Moore, 2004). By incorporating human feedback, AL allows the model to adapt to user-specific needs and

correctly identify relevant anomalies without the need to label the entire dataset.

Two AL approaches that have been implemented in the IF are the Active Learning Isolation Forest (ALIF) (Marcelli et al., 2024) and the Bayesian Active Learning Isolation Forest (BALIF) (Sartor et al., 2024). In both implementations, points are queried sequentially, meaning that the model asks for labels of informative points from the user one at a time. This setup requires frequent interactions with the domain expert, which can be inefficient and time-consuming due to the high cost and inconvenience associated with frequent involvement of the expert (Shin et al., 2024). Hence, from a user perspective, it is desirable to label a batch of points at once, which have been selected by the model jointly before. Batch querying would significantly reduce the frequency of user interactions, enhancing the usability of BALIF in real-world applications.

Although a naive approach to batch querying could involve simultaneously selecting the top k most interesting points, this strategy introduces two potential issues. First, it ignores the correlation between updates, as labeling one point might alter the informativeness of other points. Second, this approach can be particularly inefficient when the dataset contains duplicates, potentially leading to repeated queries and thereby decreasing the overall informativeness of the queried batch.

Bayesian Active Learning by Disagreement (BALD) (Houlsby et al., 2011) is a querying strategy for Bayesian models, initially introduced for a Gaussian Process Classifier, which is based on information gain, and has been extended to batch querying in a Deep Learning setting as BatchBALD (Kirsch et al., 2019). Their probabilistic frameworks make both querying methods ideal candidates

for BALIF, with BatchBALD specifically for the batch querying problem.

This work explores and compares different batch querying strategies for BALIF. We derive a closed-form solution of the BALD and BatchBALD querying strategies for BALIF and compare it to a heuristic-based method using the native BALIF interest scores. Our experiments demonstrate that our robust-worst-case method is superior in performance, while being more flexible and less computationally expensive.

2. RELATED WORK

2.1 BALIF

The Bayesian Active Learning Isolation Forest (BALIF) is a probabilistic AD algorithm based on the popular IF with an AL strategy (Sartor et al., 2024). The IF (Liu et al., 2009) is an unsupervised ensemble approach composed of multiple decision trees. Each tree in the ensemble aims to quickly identify outliers by randomly splitting the feature space until the samples become isolated or a maximum depth is reached. The decision tree predictions are made based on node depth, assuming that outliers take on average fewer splits to separate than normal points, i.e., are more likely to reside in leaves closer to the root.

Although IF is an unsupervised model, recent extensions that support AL have been proposed, namely Active Learning Isolation Forest (ALIF), a weakly supervised approach, which introduces updates of the leaf nodes’ depth (Marcelli et al., 2024), and BALIF (Sartor et al., 2024), which generalizes ALIF defining a rigorous Bayesian framework for model updates.

Each decision tree in the IF ensemble defines a feature-space partition, represented by the tree leaves. This structure is preserved in ALIF and BALIF, and remains invariant during model updates. The model parameters θ model the anomaly rates of each region in each partition of the feature space. The model has one parameter θ_l for each leaf l , which represents the probability that a sample $x \in l$ is an anomaly.

$$y \mid \theta \sim \text{Bernoulli}(\theta_l) \quad (1)$$

The beliefs on the anomaly rate θ_l are described by:

$$\theta_l \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha_l, \beta_l) \quad (2)$$

According to BALIF (Sartor et al., 2024), the parameters α_l, β_l are initialized based on the depth-based anomaly score of IF and can be modified to update the model using labeled data. Given a labeled sample x with true label \hat{y} , the belief distribution is updated only for the leaves l that contain x :

$$\theta_l \mid \hat{y} \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha_l + \hat{y}, \beta_l + 1 - \hat{y}) \quad (3)$$

Similarly, for a sample x , the ensemble predictive distribution G_x is obtained by aggregating only the parameters of the leaves that contain it:

$$y \sim G_x = \text{Beta}(\nu_x \mu_x, \nu_x(1 - \mu_x)) \quad (4)$$

where $\mu_x = \mathbb{E}_{l \ni x} \left[\frac{\alpha_l}{\alpha_l + \beta_l} \right]$ and $\nu_x = \sum_{l \ni x} (\alpha_l + \beta_l)$ are the mean and sample size of the Beta distribution, respectively.

For AL, Sartor et al. (2024) propose two heuristic query strategies based on the distribution $G_x(z)$. The *most anomalous* strategy defines the interest score as the anomaly score given by the model, which in the case of BALIF is the mean of G_x .

$$\text{IS}_{\text{ANOM}}(x) = \mathbb{E}_{z \sim G_x} [z] = \mu_x \quad (5)$$

The *likelihood margin* strategy is specific to BALIF and is used to preferentially query samples near the decision boundary. For a given threshold r , the interest score is defined as the likelihood ratio between the mode and r :

$$\text{IS}_{\text{MARGIN}}(x) = -\frac{\max_z G_x(z)}{G_x(r)} \quad (6)$$

2.2 BALD

BALD (Houlsby et al., 2011) is an AL approach that selects data points based on the mutual information gain between model prediction and model parameters. The core intuition is that querying for samples whose predictions are strongly coupled to the model parameters will provide the most useful label for refining the model.

Let θ denote the model parameters and let $p(\theta)$ be the posterior distribution. For an unlabeled input x , BALD quantifies how informative its label would be by computing the conditional mutual information between the posterior predictive distribution over y and the posterior distribution over θ . The interest score is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{IS}_{\text{BALD}}(x) &= I(y; \theta) \\ &= H(y) - \mathbb{E}_{\theta \sim p(\theta)} [H(y \mid \theta)] \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The first term in Equation 7 represents the general uncertainty of the prediction of the model, which reflects the confidence in the predicted label of x . The second term expresses the expected entropy of the predictions made by individual model configurations, obtained by sampling θ from its posterior distribution. To achieve high mutual information, the first term must be high, which means that the model is not confident about its prediction of the label of x . At the same time, the second term has to be low, indicating that individual draws of the model parameters give confident predictions.

These two conditions can only occur simultaneously when different model configurations are confident about their predictions but disagree with one another. This disagreement among confident predictions suggests that observing the true label of the queried point can help inform the model parameters.

2.3 BatchBALD

In practice, top-k batch selection for BALD involves selecting the points that yield the highest total interest score, i.e. have the highest mutual information $I(y_i; \theta)$:

$$\text{IS}_{\text{BALD top-k}}(x_1, \dots, x_k) = \sum_{i=1}^k I(y_i; \theta) \quad (8)$$

However, this method assumes that each point contributes information independently, ignoring dependencies or similarities among selected points. As a result, the selected batch may include redundant or similar points, which reduces its overall effectiveness.

BatchBALD (Kirsch et al., 2019) is an extension of BALD that addresses this limitation by evaluating how informative a set of points is jointly, rather than individually. Instead of summing mutual information scores across points, BatchBALD computes the mutual information between the set of predicted labels and the model parameters:

$$\text{IS}_{\text{BatchBALD}}(x_1, \dots, x_k) = I(y_1, \dots, y_k; \theta) \quad (9)$$

This approach avoids selecting redundant points by accounting for correlations between points within a batch, leading to more diverse and informative queries compared to BALD, particularly when handling datasets containing repeated or similar data points.

However, computing the exact joint mutual information over all possible batches of points is computationally expensive, especially as we increase the batch size. To avoid this, BatchBALD uses a greedy approximation that selects points one at a time. At each iteration, the next point is chosen on the basis of its contribution to the mutual information, given the points already selected. This avoids the need to evaluate all combinations and still provides a close approximation to the optimal batch, as demonstrated in Kirsch et al. (2019).

3. METHODS

3.1 Closed-form BALD in BALIF

Given the explicit form of the probabilistic anomaly rates in BALIF in Equation 1, a closed-form expression for the BALD interest scores in Equation 7 can be derived. Thus, unlike in Kirsch et al. (2019), there is no need for Monte Carlo sampling.

Considering a single tree in the ensemble, the posterior predictive distribution can be obtained from Equation 1:

$$y \sim \text{Bernoulli}\left(\frac{\alpha_l}{\alpha_l + \beta_l}\right) \quad (10)$$

Therefore the entropy of the prediction is expressed as:

$$H(y) = -\frac{\alpha_l}{\alpha_l + \beta_l} \log\left(\frac{\alpha_l}{\alpha_l + \beta_l}\right) - \frac{\beta_l}{\alpha_l + \beta_l} \log\left(\frac{\beta_l}{\alpha_l + \beta_l}\right) \quad (11)$$

The conditional entropy term can be expressed in closed form using the digamma function ψ :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}_{\theta \sim p(\theta)}[H(y | \theta)] &= \mathbb{E}_{\theta_l \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha_l, \beta_l)}[H(y | \theta_l)] \\ &= +\psi(\alpha_l + \beta_l + 1) - \frac{\alpha_l \psi(\alpha_l + 1) + \beta_l \psi(\beta_l + 1)}{\alpha_l + \beta_l} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

3.2 Closed-form BatchBALD in BALIF

BatchBALD can be adapted to the BALIF framework in a similar way as BALD. For BatchBALD, we need to consider the joint entropy and joint conditional entropies.

Given a single tree in the BALIF ensemble and a batch of points with predictions y_1, \dots, y_k , predictions for points in different leaves will be independent and the total entropy can be expressed as the sum of entropies of individual leaves:

$$H(y_1, \dots, y_k) = \sum_l H(y_{l_1}, \dots, y_{l_{n_l}}). \quad (13)$$

Note that the posterior predictive distribution for points in the same leaf is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}(y_{l_1}, \dots, y_{l_{n_l}}) &= \mathbb{E}_{\theta} \left[\mathbb{P}(y_{l_1}, \dots, y_{l_{n_l}} | \theta) \right] \\ &= \frac{B(\alpha_l + m_l, \beta_l + n_l - m_l)}{B(\alpha_l, \beta_l)} = \frac{\alpha_l^{(m_l)} \beta_l^{(n_l - m_l)}}{(\alpha_l + \beta_l)^{(n_l)}} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where $x^{(n)} = \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} (x+i)$ denotes the rising factorial, $m_l = \sum_{i=1}^{n_l} y_i$ is the number of anomalies and $B(\alpha, \beta)$ is the Beta function.

By grouping all terms with the same value of m_l we can express the entropy for leaf predictions as:

$$\begin{aligned} H(y_{l_1}, \dots, y_{l_{n_l}}) &= -\sum_{y_1, \dots, y_{n_l}} \mathbb{P}(y_1, \dots, y_{n_l}) \log \mathbb{P}(y_1, \dots, y_{n_l}) \\ &= -\sum_{m_l=0}^{n_l} \binom{n_l}{m_l} \frac{\alpha_l^{(m_l)} \beta_l^{(n_l - m_l)}}{(\alpha_l + \beta_l)^{(n_l)}} \log \left(\frac{\alpha_l^{(m_l)} \beta_l^{(n_l - m_l)}}{(\alpha_l + \beta_l)^{(n_l)}} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

The computation of the conditional entropy term is more straightforward. Since y_i are conditionally independent on θ , the conditional entropy can be factorized as:

$$\mathbb{E}_{\theta \sim p(\theta)}[H(y_1, \dots, y_k | \theta)] = \sum_{i=1}^k \mathbb{E}_{\theta \sim p(\theta)}[H(y_i | \theta)] \quad (16)$$

where each term of the sum can be computed as in Equation 12.

The mutual information over the entire ensemble can be computed as the sum of the mutual information calculated for each tree, assuming independence among trees, as already assumed in the original BALIF paper. However, it is still computationally expensive to evaluate the mutual information for each possible batch of points, so we adopt the same greedy strategy of BatchBALD (Kirsch et al., 2019), as described in section 2.3.

3.3 Robust-Worst-Case Batch Querying

The approach taken by Kirsch et al. (2019) to adapt the BALD interest score to batch query cannot be replicated for other strategies. For this reason, we propose the *robust-worst-case* (RWC) strategy, which can be used to adapt any sequential query strategy to work in a batch query setting. The approach follows the same greedy procedure described in section 2.3, but takes a conservative approach to the selection of each new sample.

The first candidate sample is selected maximizing the interest score of choice $x_1 = \arg \max_x \text{IS}(x)$. The best next sample to add to the batch is highly dependent on the label \hat{y}_1 that will be acquired, which is not known at this stage. To take this dependence into consideration, the model is updated for both $\hat{y}_1 = 0$ and $\hat{y}_1 = 1$, then the interest score is computed using each updated model. The RWC strategy defines the interest score for the next sample as the minimum interest score across the two possible scenarios.

In general, given a partial batch of already selected samples x_1, \dots, x_j , the next sample is chosen based on the worst possible labeling scenario:

$$\text{IS}_{\text{RWC}}(x; x_1, \dots, x_j) = \min_{\hat{y}_1, \dots, \hat{y}_j} \text{IS}(x | \hat{y}_1, \dots, \hat{y}_j) \quad (17)$$

Fig. 1. Interest scores as a function of α and β for different querying strategies. Starting from the star before the update, the black lines indicate different but constant sample sizes after an update, where only values on the solid black line are achievable, since an update only increases the parameters. The interest scores are uni-modal along the lines of constant sample sizes, and the minima must be found at one of the extrema of the achievable interval.

Taking into consideration all possible realizations of $\hat{y}_1, \dots, \hat{y}_j$ has exponential complexity in batch size. However, the worst-case can be computed in constant time for most interest score functions based on the predictive distribution G_x in Equation 4. In fact, inserting the expression for the model updates from Equation 3 into Equation 17, the sample size of G_x is given by:

$$\nu_x = \sum_{l \ni x} \left(\alpha_l + \beta_l + \sum_{i=1}^j \mathbb{1}_{x_i \in l} \right) \quad (18)$$

Notably, ν_x does not depend on the value of the acquired labels. Thus, calculating the interest scores for all the possible model updates in Equation 17 involves only distributions with the same sample size ν_x but different means μ_x .

If the interest score function used is unimodal along lines of constant sample size, then the worst-case, i.e. the minimum interest score, can be achieved only for the extreme cases where $\hat{y}_1, \dots, \hat{y}_j$ all have the same value. These considerations lead to a significant reduction in complexity, since only two cases need to be considered, instead of an exponential number of combinations.

As shown in Figure 1, the BALD interest score in Equation 7 is unimodal for a fixed sample size. Similarly, both strategies proposed in Sartor et al. (2024) are also unimodal for a fixed sample size. Thus all three strategies can benefit from this efficient implementation.

4. EXPERIMENTS

We evaluate the proposed AL batch-querying strategies on well-established AD datasets (Shebty, 2016). For each experiment, we performed a 50-50 stratified split into training and test sets, where AL is conducted on the training set and the average precision evaluated on the test set. As the batch-querying problem is more prominent in datasets with real or near-duplicates, we duplicate the training set similarly to Kirsch et al. (2019). We set both the number of duplicates and batch size equal to 10 and conduct the AL until 10% of the total training set has been labeled. Each experiment is repeated 10 times with different seeds and standard hyperparameters to obtain an estimate of uncertainty.

We compare the performance of different batch query strategies as a function of the number of labeled data points. We use Average Precision (AP) as the metric of choice as it best reflects performance for imbalanced datasets, since it focuses on precision and recall rather than on false positive/negative rates.

The code to reproduce the experimental evaluation and figures can be found at github.com/AMCO-UniPD/balif.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results in Figure 2 show that RWC strategies consistently outperform their top-k counterparts on all datasets, which validates the method as a suitable strategy for batch querying. Within the RWC querying strategies, the MARGIN method appears to perform better or comparable to BALD, which is especially pronounced for the **letter** and **vowel** datasets. For the **breastw** and **satimage-2** datasets, all strategies achieve similar performance, which can be attributed to the high initial performance of the unsupervised IF, leaving little room for incremental improvements. Interestingly, for **pima**, the random query is as good as the RWC strategies, which cannot be explained by high initial performance.

The dataset size appears to influence the performance of the strategies: BALD RWC appears to be susceptible to constant performance after few initial queries on medium and large datasets, from **vowels** and larger. The MARGIN RWC strategy is consistently a top performer in small datasets, while significantly outperforming all other strategies in larger datasets, indicating that the MARGIN RWC strategy is especially effective for medium and large datasets. This is not observed for BALD RWC, indicating that BALD comparably does not scale well with the dataset size. Even in the domain of small datasets, BALD does not have a clear advantage over the MARGIN interest score.

Although the RWC strategy and BatchBALD were both developed for batch-querying settings with duplicates in the dataset, BatchBALD performs worse than or similar to a random query across all datasets. This result is in line with expected poor performance of BatchBALD on

Fig. 2. Comparison of the average precision of different batch-querying strategies across datasets, ordered by increasing dataset size. The shaded area denotes the standard deviation across experiment repetitions. The RWC strategy clearly outperforms all other strategies, while BatchBALD consistently achieves lower average precision than random querying. The MARGIN interest score scales better than BALD for medium to large datasets.

unbalanced datasets, as noted by Kirsch et al. (2019), and confirms that BatchBALD is indeed not suitable for AD. However, the closed form BatchBALD interest score considers each tree in the ensemble separately, rather than the forest as a whole, which could also be a contributing factor to the poor performance.

Thus, the MARGIN interest score with the RWC batch query strategy appears to be better than the other strategies considering all important aspects, namely performance, scalability, and time complexity.

6. CONCLUSION

Driven by the practical need in AL to optimize the expert's time and to label several points jointly, we address the challenge of batch-querying in BALIF (Sartor et al., 2024). Therefore, we develop a novel and efficient strategy for batch query in BALIF named robust-worst-case (RWC). This method is based on a conservative estimate of the interest score, maximizing the interest score for the worst possible result for the queried labels, ensuring that the queried points are relevant independently of the yet unknown labels of the other points in the batch.

We demonstrate the effectiveness of the RWC batch querying strategy, particularly on datasets containing duplicates. Its scalability on larger datasets appears to be influenced by the choice of interest score used within the strategy. The margin interest score employed by BALIF (Sartor et al., 2024) under this querying approach delivers strong performance, supporting its practical deployment and enhancing user acceptance in real-world applications.

Future work should assess the influence of batch size, data redundancy, and general dataset characteristics on the applicability of the RWC batch-querying strategy. Further research on the theoretic requirements and limitations due to different interest scores, as well as validation on real-world datasets are necessary.

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